

Report of Zoonoses, Alimentary and Water-Borne Infections in the Slovak Republic in 2022

1. *Salmonella* spp.

Salmonella is a zoonotic pathogen whose risks for both humans and animals has long been of high concern. Its disease symptoms include nausea, diarrhoea, fever and abdominal cramps. The main sources of infection are eggs and undercooked food of animal origin, but there is also an upward trend in the risk of salmonella infection from keeping reptiles and exotic species. Across all European Union countries, in 2020 there were 52,702 cases of disease, of which 57 were fatal.

There were 3,762 reported cases of Salmonellosis in Slovakia in 2022, which is 17.2% lower than in 2021 and 29% lower than the five-year average. Cases were reported in all regions, with the highest morbidity being in the Prešov, Košice and Žilina Regions. There were 105 outbreaks of which 14 were of a larger size. Family outbreaks affecting 2 to 4 family members accounted for 91 outbreaks. *S. Enteritidis* was the most common cause of infections and outbreaks.

Fig. 1 Incidence of Salmonellosis by District in Slovakia in 2022

The official control authorities examined 10,901 foodstuffs in 2022, of which 0.46% were positive, compared to 0.20% in the previous year. A higher percentage of positive samples was found in unspecified poultry meat (14.34%). No evidence of salmonella was found in ice cream and frozen desserts, delicatessen products, confectionery or sweets. A total of 7 serovars were identified in foodstuffs, of which the most frequent were *S. Infantis* (54%) and *S. Newport* (30%).

Authorities examined 6,201 clinical samples from animals for the presence of *Salmonella* spp. in 2022. Of these, 4,602 poultry flocks were examined with a positive finding in 1.1% of the flocks, dominated by *S. Infantis* and *S. Enteritidis*. In farm animals, 319 samples from cattle were tested and salmonella was found in 2.82%. There was no positive sample in sheep, goats or horses. In pigs, one sample returned a positive result. Among pets, samples were examined mainly from dogs, where 1.7% of 641 samples were positive. Tests were carried out on 180

samples from cats, with a positivity rate of 2.2%. The serovar *S. Infantis* dominated, followed by *S. Typhimurium*. In the group of birds other than poultry, the prevalence was higher (7%), in line with expectations. The dominant serovar was *S. Newlands*. Of the total number of 6,201 examined clinical samples from animals, 91 were positive (1.47%). The highest rate of positive samples was in poultry (*Gallus gallus*), namely 0.8%. The serovar *S. Infantis* was most frequent, followed by the serovar *S. Enteritidis*.

In 2022, a total of 816 feed or feed mixtures were examined for the presence of *Salmonella* spp., with 9 samples returning positive results. Out of 597 samples of feed of animal origin, organic fertilizers and swabs from establishments, *Salmonella* spp. was confirmed in 8 samples, whereas in the category of other feeds, 1 of 79 samples tested positive with the serovar *S. Pomona*.

Out of 5,524 examined samples from the external environment and water, 0.91% were positive for the presence of *Salmonella* spp. in 2022.

There were no significant differences compared to previous years in 2022. The most frequently isolated strains from broilers were *S. Infantis* (30 isolates) and *S. Enteritidis* (6 isolates). Tetracycline resistance was observed in 77% of *S. Infantis* isolates. Most isolates of *S. Enteritidis* were fully susceptible, except for 2 isolates resistant to nalidixic acid and 1 isolate resistant to tetracycline and ciprofloxacin. *S. Szentes* was fully susceptible to the tested antimicrobials.

2. *Escherichia coli*

Escherichia coli is an important part of the intestinal microbiota in humans and other animals. There is a significant risk of food poisoning when strains of *E. coli* produce verocytotoxins / Shiga toxins (VTEC/STEC). They are transmitted through contaminated food and water, contact with animals and direct contact between people. The incubation period is 3 to 9 days. Haemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS), which is characterised by kidney failure, has an incubation period of up to 7 days. HUS develops in 7% of VTEC/STEC infections.

In 2022 there were 297 reports of *E. coli* infection in Slovakia, the most common form being enteropathogenic *E. coli* (290 cases). One minor outbreak was recorded. Nosocomial infection was reported in a total of 10 cases.

In total, 4,308 food samples were analysed, with a positivity rate of 9.2%. The highest positivity was recorded in the case of dairy products. Of 15,734 water samples, lakes and rivers registered the highest positive rate. In the category of other samples, sandpits had a remarkable positivity of 10%.

A total of 57 samples were tested for STEC using molecular methods, all with negative results. However, EPEC was detected in two samples, with one being identified as serogroup O26. In one case, haemolytic *Escherichia coli* was detected in tested culture isolates from ready-to-eat foods and water.

The level of microbial resistance in commensal *Escherichia coli* in poultry caecal samples ranged from 0% to 89%, with 5 of the 85 tested profiles displaying susceptibility to all tested antimicrobials. In 69% of poultry and porcine caecal samples, *E. coli* produced broad-spectrum β -lactamases such as ESBL and AmpC. Meat samples tested for commensal *Escherichia coli* had a positive rate of 75% (chicken > turkey > pork > beef). The incidence of *E. coli* producing ESBL and AmpC ranged from 2% to 53%. In the case of beef, the positivity for ESBL and AmpC producing *E. coli* has been in ranged between 2% and 7% since 2015 (reaching 7% in 2021). In pork, positivity has been on an upward trend since 2015, but it remained at the same level as in 2021 (19%). The presence of a carbapenemase producer (CARBA) was not confirmed in any of the tested samples.

E. coli resistance was also analysed in a wastewater sample, where resistance to gentamicin and tetracycline was determined among the tested antimicrobials.

3. *Yersinia* spp.

The genus *Yersinia* consists of 21 species of which 3 are pathogenic for humans – *Y. pestis*, which is transmitted by fleas and causes plague, *Y. pseudotuberculosis*, the aetiological factor of pseudotuberculosis, and *Y. enterocolitica*, which mainly causes gastrointestinal disease. The main risk factors are undercooked pork, poultry, meat products, raw milk, infected plants, tofu, seafood and polluted water. It can also be transmitted from person to person. Yersinosis was the third-most frequently reported alimentary zoonosis in the EU in 2020, with 5,668 cases and 2 deaths. There were 16 recorded outbreaks in 6 EU countries.

A total of 288 cases were reported in 2022, which is 37.1% more than the year before. The highest morbidity was in the age categories of 0 years and from 1 to 4 years. Cases were reported in all regions with the highest morbidity in the Trenčín Region and the lowest morbidity in the Trnava Region. A monitoring programme for *Yersinia enterocolitica* in chilled pork was implemented in 2022 in line with the National Action Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance in the Slovak Republic (57 samples). Culture results confirmed *Yersinia enterocolitica* contamination in 19 samples.

A total of 25 clinical samples were tested for *Yersinia enterocolitica*, which was confirmed in a cow colostrum pool comprising 3 cattle samples. A monitoring programme for *Yersinia enterocolitica* in porcine caecum was implemented in 2022 in accordance with the National Action Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance in the Slovak Republic, involving 48 samples. Culture results confirmed *Yersinia enterocolitica* contamination in 4 samples.

4. *Cronobacter* spp.

Cronobacter spp. is a genus of Gram-negative facultatively anaerobic bacteria. The species in this genus cause rare but life-threatening infections of infants. New-born babies with a low birth weight are the most vulnerable but the disease can also affect older people and immunocompromised people. Disease symptoms include irritability, jaundice, hoarse breathing, fluctuating body temperature. Meningitis can develop. Death occurs in 50% of new-born children within several hours or days. The main cause is contaminated dried baby formula.

No cases of human diseases were recorded in 2022. A total of 786 samples of first infant formula and follow-on infant formula were analysed to detect these bacteria and *Cronobacter* spp. was confirmed four times in one sample of first infant formula for infants aged 0-6 months in powder form with added goat milk proteins from a foreign manufacturer.

5. *Shigella* spp.

The genus *Shigella* consists of rod-shaped bacteria belonging to the family *Enterobacteriaceae*, and is the causative agent of shigellosis, an intestinal infection. The characteristics of *Shigella* bacteria include adherence, invasion, intracellular reproduction and cell-to-cell spread. Infection is spread via the faecal-oral route, direct contact with infected individuals, contaminated food, water or objects.

A total of 183 cases of sickness were reported in 2022, which represents a 40.8% increase in the comparison with 2021 though it is still 5% below the five-year average. The highest age-specific morbidity was reported in the age groups of 0 years and 1-4 years. The causal agent was *Shigella flexneri* in 90 cases and *Shigella sonnei* in 67 cases. Three outbreaks were recorded, all within families. Three samples of gelatine were tested for *Shigella* spp. in 2022. None returned a positive result. Water was not analysed for this parameter.

6. *Plesiomonas shigelloides*

The genus *Plesiomonas* consists of a single species *Plesiomonas shigelloides*, which causes intestinal disease. Its clinical symptoms are fever, diarrhoea, abdominal pain, vomiting, nausea, chills and headache. Infection is spread via the faecal-oral route, contaminated water, contaminated food and from person to person.

Samples of surface water and the environment were not analysed to detect *Plesiomonas shigelloides* in particular in 2022.

7. Legionella spp.

Legionella bacteria are a part of freshwater microbial ecosystems. They exist in symbiosis with other bacteria and amoebas, especially in biofilms. They also find good conditions for survival and reproduction in water supply systems (e.g. indoor plumbing, water attractions). Researchers have so far identified 61 species of legionella, 28 of which are associated with human disease. A person can become infected by inhaling a contaminated water aerosol. Infection can lead to a severe life-threatening pneumonia, Legionnaire's disease, which is fatal in 8–10% of cases, or an influenza-like disease, Pontiac fever.

Legionnaire's disease (LD) has been on the rise in Slovakia since 2014. In 2022, there were 132 cases of LD, 76% of which were in patients over the age of 50. In 35% of patients, coinfection with the SARS-Cov-2 virus was recorded. The mortality rate for LD patients was 8%, which rose to 17% for patients with SARS-Cov-2 coinfection. Pontiac fever was diagnosed in 21 patients.

A total of 693 water samples, 112 swabs from the aquatic environment and 36 air samples and swabs from air-conditioning equipment were tested for the presence of Legionella in the environment. Legionella were detected in 25.8% of the examined samples. Epidemiological investigations to trace infection pathways were carried out with 27 patients, which was just over a fifth of cases.

8. Vibrio spp.

Vibrio is a genus of bacteria that move using a whip-like appendage. As pathogens, the most severe risk is associated with *Vibrio cholerae* serotypes O1 and O139, which produce the cholera toxin and cause cholera epidemics. Thanks to rigorous hygiene, there has been no endemic cholera in Europe for a long time and it occurs only as an imported infection. Serotypes of *V. cholerae* non O1 non O139 cause diarrhoeic diseases. People can become infected during recreational activity in water or through the food chain. The genus *Vibrio* includes another 12 species that can cause disease in humans, including *V. vulnificus*, which causes gastroenteritis, *V. parahaemolyticus* which causes alimentary intoxication, *V. fluvialis* and *V. furnissi*, which cause infection of skin, wounds and soft tissues.

As in previous years, no cases of cholera were reported in 2022. There were three cases of middle ear infection caused by *Vibrio alginolyticus*, two cases of diarrhoeal diseases caused by *Vibrio fluvialis* and one case in which *Vibrio* sp. were isolated from the patient's stool together with *Aeromonas* sp.

A total of 62 samples various foodstuffs were examined. Several *Vibrio* species were isolated, including *V. parahaemolyticus* in one case. Several species were found in surface waters used for bathing, especially during the summer season when the water is warmer. The presence of *V. cholerae* and regular findings of *V. fluvialis* and *V. furnissii* in the water in Slovakia is a cause for concern because these pathogens are usually found in coastal regions, and their appearance in our territory is probably linked to the warming climate.

9. Aeromonas spp.

Bacteria of the genus *Aeromonas* live in wastewater, in soil and organic matter residues. They can also survive in chlorinated drinking water or colonise the intestinal tracts of various animals. They are pathogens for humans and animals. They cause disease by releasing a cytotoxic enterotoxin and through surface adhesion and invasion. Aeromonad-induced disease may present as a gastrointestinal or extraintestinal infection.

In 2022, the Regional Public Health Authority in Komárno analysed 13 isolates from the stools of patients with severe diarrhoeic disease and confirmed *Aeromonas* in 10 of them. There

was one extraintestinal infection involving *A. caviae*. Water samples revealed 173 strains, with *A. hydrophila* accounting for 67.4% of finds. In 2022, the VFI in Dolný Kubín analysed 67 samples (fish, leeches, cattle organs) and confirmed the presence of *Aeromonas* spp. in 13 of 22 fish samples.

10. *Campylobacter* spp.

The genus *Campylobacter* can cause intestinal infections in people and miscarriages in livestock. These bacteria have reservoirs in the digestive tracts of domestic and wild animals. The transmission route can be faecal-oral, person-to-person, sexual contact or the consumption of contaminated food or water. The infective dose is relatively low. The incubation period is 2–5 days. The most common clinical symptoms are diarrhoea, abdominal pain, fever, headache and muscle pain and possibly also vomiting. After recovering from acute enteritis, patients may develop neurological disorders. Campylobacteriosis has been the most reported gastrointestinal disease in the EU since 2005, and in Slovakia since 2011.

A total of 4,788 cases of campylobacteriosis were reported in 2022, with its highest incidence being in the Prešov Region. The infection was imported in 21 cases. The authorities recorded 18 minor outbreaks involving 2 – 3 cases. The most frequent agent in these infections and outbreaks was *C. jejuni*.

Fig. 2 Incidence of *Campylobacter* Enteritis by District in Slovakia in 2022

Analysis of 503 tested food samples – mainly from food of animal origin – confirmed the presence of *Campylobacter jejuni* in 33 samples of fresh broiler meat, giving a positivity rate of 6.6%.

Examination of 1,569 samples of clinical material from animals for the presence of *Campylobacter* spp., returned a positive finding in 13 % of cases. The main pathogenic agent in pigs was *C. coli*, which made up 90% of positive porcine samples. *C. jejuni* was the most common species in pets, accounting for 90% and 95% of positive samples in cats and dogs respectively.

Of 85 tested isolates of *Campylobacter jejuni*, none was resistant to gentamicin and one isolate was resistant to erythromycin. A higher level of resistance, though still below 50%, was observed against tetracycline(48%R). The isolates exhibited high levels of resistance to fluoroquinolone antimicrobials (ciprofloxacin 85%R). Of the 27 *Campylobacter coli* isolates

tested, all were susceptible to erythromycin, gentamicin and chloramphenicol; resistance to tetracycline was estimated at 60% and to ciprofloxacin at 100%.

11. *Brucella* spp.

Bacteria from the genus *Brucella* are the cause of the zoonotic disease brucellosis. The source of infection is an infected animal or on rare occasions a person and it is transmitted through direct contact with the infectious animal, contaminated food or an inhaled aerosol. Typical foods for the alimentary route of infection are meat, raw milk and products made from them. After penetrating the skin, mucous membranes or digestive tract, the *Brucella* bacteria multiply in the lymph nodes and then attack other organs through the bloodstream. The pathogenicity of these bacteria is determined by endotoxins. In 2020, there were 128 reported cases of brucellosis in European Union countries and two reported deaths. The pathogenic agent was *Brucella melitensis* in 88% of cases.

In the ten years to 2020, no more than one case per year was reported in Slovakia and then in 2020 there were seven cases of disease followed by six cases in 2021. In 2022 there were three reports of sickness, all from the Banská Bystrica Region.

Slovakia is officially free of the incidence of bovine, ovine and caprine brucellosis. To maintain this status, the authorities conducted 68,672 serological tests of cattle and 16,336 serological tests of sheep and goats.

12. *Anaplasma phagocytophilum*

A. phagocytophilum is a species of bacteria in the genus *Rickettsiales*, which is a cause of granulocytic anaplasmosis in humans and animals. The primary vector is the tick *Ixodes ricinus*. The bacteria attack granulocytes (white blood cells) in the host's blood and undermine their immune system. The incubation period is one to three weeks from the tick bite. Symptoms of infection include headache, muscle pain, sweating, weakness and a high temperature. In animals, it causes granulocytic anaplasmosis of dogs and horses while in ruminants it causes tick-borne fever.

In 2022, *A. phagocytophilum* was confirmed in blood samples from the patients of infectious disease clinics in Slovakia in two cases. A high prevalence of infection was observed in cervine animals (68%). An overall prevalence of 16.79% was recorded in ticks. The presence of the bacterium was confirmed in one sample of tick DNA from a patient. Analysis of four tick DNA samples taken from dogs confirmed *A. phagocytophilum* in two cases.

13. *Coxiella burnetii*

The intracellular bacteria *C. burnetii* are a pathogenic agent for the zoonotic disease Q fever. Most human infections come from ruminants. Infection most often occurs through inhalation of contaminated aerosols or dust, contact with infected animals or consumption of contaminated milk. The incubation period of the disease is 20 days. The acute form can produce high fever, headaches, weakness and shivering. It is fatal in 2% of cases. There is also a less common chronic form that is associated with complications such as endocarditis or liver disorders.

Since an epidemic in 1993, there have been only sporadic cases of the disease in Slovakia. After two reports of disease from the Bratislava Region in 2021, no cases were reported in 2022. The BMC Institute of Virology at the Slovak Academy of Sciences tested serum samples from 165 patients. There was no indication that any of the patients had overcome Q fever or were suffering acute Q fever based on tests for antibodies against *Coxiella burnetii* phase II. Analysis of 1,202 samples from cattle, goats and sheep returned positive serological findings only in the case of cattle, with a positivity rate of 2.09%. There have been no positive serological findings in goats in recent years (most recently in 2010 and 2013) while there have long been no serological positive findings in sheep.

14. *Francisella tularensis*

Tularaemia, a zoonotic disease with natural foci, is caused by *Francisella tularensis*, a tiny, facultatively intracellular Gram-negative bacterium. In its natural foci, this pathogen circulates among various species of reservoir animals. Transmission can occur through direct or indirect contact with an infected animal, inhalation of contaminated dust or aerosols, ingestion of insufficiently cooked products from infected animals, contaminated water, food, ticks and stinging insects. The disease has a varied clinical picture. Its symptoms include fever, headache and muscle or joint pain amongst others. The incubation period of tularaemia is 3 – 8 days.

Reports of human tularaemia were received from 18 EU/EEA countries in 2021 covering a total of 973 cases, of which 876 cases were reported by 16 EU countries. Sweden, Slovenia and Finland had the highest incidence in the EU, followed by Liechtenstein and Norway from outside the EU. Austria, Sweden and Finland reported finds of *F. tularensis* in wild hares in 2021, whereas EU and EEA countries report finds in animals on a voluntary basis.

The incidence of human tularaemia in Slovakia has been on a long-term downward trend since 1995. In 2020, there were 12 reports of disease (0.22 cases / 100,000 inhabitants) and in 2021 cases reached the lowest possible level, with zero reports of disease.

In 2022, there were 4 confirmed cases of tularaemia reported in Slovakia (incidence 0.074 cases / 100,000 inhabitants). One case of disease occurred before the end of 2021, was laboratory confirmed in December and reported in January 2022, while the other three cases occurred in July, August and October. Illness affected two men and two women (1:1) aged between 7 and 46 years. Two cases of disease were reported from western Slovakia, one from the Bratislava Region (Bratislava I District) and one from the Nitra region (Nitra District), giving morbidity at the regional level of 0.14 and 0.15/100,000 inhabitants respectively. The other two cases of disease were from eastern Slovakia, both from the Prešov Region (Snina and Poprad Districts) giving regional morbidity of 0.25 cases / 100,000 inhabitants.

Veterinary services recorded two outbreaks of hare tularaemia in 2022. The VFI in Bratislava conducted tests for antibodies against *F. tularensis* on 32 field hare blood samples from hunting in six locations in three districts in the Nitra and Trnava Regions and confirmed the bacteria's presence in two sample (6.25%). They came from locations in the districts of Nitra and Šaľa, both in the Nitra Region, in a part of south-western Slovakia where *F. tularensis* is known to be endemic. The veterinary services in Slovakia detected no outbreak of hare tularaemia in the preceding two years, but only a small number of samples were analysed.

Surveillance results point to the persistence of natural foci of tularaemia with circulation of *Francisella tularensis* in the endemic area of western Slovakia and the possibility of exposure with the risk of infection by various transmission mechanisms even outside the endemic areas.

15. *Leptospira* spp.

Bacteria of the genus *Leptospira* are spiral-shaped Gram-negative bacteria that cause the zoonotic disease leptospirosis. The most important *Leptospira* reservoirs are rodents, cattle and pigs. Animal infections are mostly asymptomatic, though it can cause abortions or sterility in cattle and pigs. Infected animals shed *Leptospira* bacteria in their urine for months or years. Humans can be infected directly, through contact with an infected animal, or indirectly, for example through urine-contaminated water or soil. Leptospirosis can take the form of life-threatening hepatitis, meningitis, or flu-like diseases but it may also manifest as a subclinical infection. In severe cases, the disease can be fatal.

In 2022, one case of leptospirosis was reported in Slovakia (incidence 0.02 cases / 100,000). The patient was a man in the 25–34 age group from the Žilina Region. The disease was moderately severe and occurred in June.

A total of 548 animal blood samples were analysed, of which 2.7% were positive. Positive findings were reported from pigs, sheep and dogs. The highest positivity rate was recorded in pigs (10.1%).

16. *Borrelia* spp.

Bacteria of the genus *Borrelia* are spirochetes that cause diseases in humans and animals. They are classified into three groups by disease and vector. Bacteria in the first group causes relapsing fever and are transmitted by soft ticks or lice. Another group makes up the species complex *Borrelia burgdorferi* sensu lato, the causative agent of Lyme disease. The vectors of this group are hard ticks. The disease affects multiple systems within the human organism and is noted for the high variability of its clinical symptoms. The third group in the genus *Borrelia* consists of bacteria species which are phylogenetically close to those in the first group, but which are transmitted by hard ticks. In this case, the disease symptoms are fever, fatigue, joint pain and neurological symptoms.

In 2022, Slovakia had 1,378 reported cases, which is twice the total of 2021. The region with the most cases was Trenčín. The reported causes were tick bites in 806 cases and insect bites in 191 cases.

Fig. 3 Ten-Year Trend in Lyme Disease in Slovakia

In 2022, the VFI in Dolný Kubín carried out ELISA screening tests on 68 blood serum samples from dogs and obtained positive results for 13 samples, a 19.1% positivity rate. The BMC Institute of Virology at the Slovak Academy of Sciences used RT-PCR to analyse DNA from 136 human-biting ticks in 2022 and detected *Borellia* in 19.1%. This is the lowest positivity rate recorded in human-biting ticks in recent years, following rates of 27.2% in 2020 and 41.4% in 2021.

17. Chlamydia

Chlamydia are parasitic microorganisms that multiply in the cytoplasm of vertebrate cells and are the causative agents of the zoonotic disease chlamydiosis. Infections can result in varied symptoms (inflammation of the serous membrane, mucous membranes, lungs, joints, reproductive organs and nervous system). Infection during pregnancy is especially dangerous. In animals, chlamydia cause disease in both birds and mammals. *Chlamydia abortus* is one of the most significant causes of abortion and foetal losses in sheep, goats and cows in Slovakia, which can also infect humans and pose a threat to pregnancy. Transmission is possible through direct contact with animals, contact with their secretions, or by breathing in a contaminated aerosol.

No cases of mammal chlamydiosis or ornithosis (psittacosis), were reported in humans in 2022. This continues the trend of recent years, as all years since 2009 except in 2013 and 2015 had zero reports of human disease. There is however a significant risk that infections may be

escaping under different diagnoses because laboratories do not use differential diagnosis procedures.

Serum samples from 197 animals were tested for the presence of chlamydia antibodies in 2022. Of these, 4.57% were positive, specifically 9 blood samples from sheep after abortion – Fig. 23. Suspicion of abortions caused by *Chlamydia abortus* were confirmed at 3 sheep farms (in the Turčianske Teplice, Nitra and Prešov Districts). For more accurate epidemiological analysis of mammalian chlamydiosis, the requirement for serological examination of ruminants after abortion needs to be reintroduced, especially for sheep with reproductive problems, as evidenced by the statistics on sheep tested after abortion in the period 2019–2022, which showed a relatively high average seropositivity of ovine chlamydiosis around 17%. – Table 44. As regards the prevention and prophylaxis of infection, it is important to respect basic animal health principles, as infected birds and poultry are often the reservoirs of the disease. Subclinical intestinal infection is also possible and rams play an important role in the spread of the disease, as they can excrete *Chlamydia sp.* via ejaculate without symptoms and therefore breeding rams should be examined every year before breeding.

18. *Mycobacterium spp.*

Pathogenic species from the genus *Mycobacterium* are the causative agents of tuberculosis in humans and animals. Zoonotic potential comes mainly from the complex *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. Bacteria from a sick person or animal can be transmitted through the respiratory tract, contaminated food, direct contact with injured skin or through the mucous membranes. Many cases of disease are recorded in high-risk groups such as homeless people, migrants, prisoners, ethnic minorities, persons with HIV, alcoholics, drug addicts and other marginalised groups.

There were 155 reported cases of human tuberculosis in 2022, which is 18 cases more than in 2021. It is notable that the patients were aged 0 to 19 years in 34.8% of cases. As in previous years, the highest morbidity was recorded in eastern Slovakia and the lowest was in the Nitra Region.

TBC podľa regiónov Slovenska v roku 2022

Fig. 4 Incidence of Tuberculosis in Regions of Slovakia and Surrounding Countries in 2022

In the field of animal health, the Slovak Republic continues to have the official status of a country free of bovine tuberculosis. For suspicion of infection with *Mycobacterium avium* susp.

avium, one sample from domestic pigeon organs was examined by the cultivation method at the VFI in Bratislava. The result was negative.

19. *Listeria* spp.

Listeria monocytogenes is the only known pathogenic species in this genus. It causes the zoonotic disease listeriosis, which has a high mortality rate. Rodents are a reservoir of listeria in the wild. The most common transmission pathway for humans is the consumption of contaminated food, especially raw or uncooked food. The disease presents with flu-like symptoms including fever, muscle aches and gastrointestinal discomfort. Due to the long incubation period, it is often very difficult to determine the source of infection. In 2020, there were 16 reported food-borne listeriosis outbreaks in the EU in which 120 people became ill. The outbreaks were mainly connected to fish.

A total of 25 cases of listeriosis were reported in Slovakia in 2022 (morb. 0.46/100,000), which is 11 cases more than in 2021 and 81% more than the 5-year average. There were also 2 reports of neonatal (disseminated) listeriosis. The Bratislava Region had the most cases. There were two reports of death due to an infectious cause, two reports of death probably due to an infectious cause and five reports of death due to other causes.

Tests were carried out on 8,064 samples from 31 types of food in 2022. The positivity rate was 0.99%. There was a higher positivity rate for the soft sheep's cheese *bryndza*. Positive findings came only from sheep, where the percentage of positive samples was 65.96%. Tests for listeria were carried out on 1,735 environmental swabs with a 0.73% positivity rate. In 2022 as in previous years, the most frequently isolated serotype in food was serotype 1/2a, which accounted for 81.1%. Although serotype 1/2a is the most frequently isolated serotype from food, most human outbreaks are caused by serotype 4b, which made up 2.7% of all serotypes from food in 2022.

20. *Bacillus anthracis*

Bacteria of the species *Bacillus anthracis* are the causative agent of splenic anthrax, which is a primary disease of ruminants, but can affect all mammals, including humans. Anthrax spores can survive in the environment for more than 100 years, making contaminated soil or animal raw materials a permanent source of infection. The human disease varies according to the site of infection and has three main forms – skin, gastrointestinal and pulmonary. Anthrax is a rare disease in EU countries.

Between 2016 and 2021, EU/EEC countries reported 22 cases of the disease. In June 2022, 100 cattle died from anthrax in Croatia and 6 people became infected.

The last cases of anthrax in Slovakia were in 2003 for humans and in 2014 for animals. In 2022, the authorities analysed 16 samples of raw materials from the leather industry and 3 suspect packages, none of which were found contain spores of *B. anthracis*.

21. *Clostridium* spp.

The bacterial genus *Clostridium* causes various types of disease in humans and animals. The basis of this pathogenicity is the production of exotoxins. *Cl. botulinum* is the causative agent of botulism in humans and animals. Death occurs on the 2nd to 5th day after ingestion; the mortality rate is 17 – 80%. In 2020, there were 80 cases of botulism in 12 EU countries, including 46 in Italy. *Cl. perfringens* is a common cause of food poisoning. The incubation period is 6 – 24 hours. The disease symptoms are cramps, diarrhoea and sometimes fever and vomiting. *Cl. perfringens* causes intestinal diseases in animals, especially young ones. Another group of clostridia cause wound infections. These include *Cl. perfringens*, *Cl. septicum*, *Cl. histolyticum*, *Cl. Novyi*, *Cl. sordelli* and *Cl. tetani*.

In 2022, *Cl. botulinum* and *Cl. perfringens* were not identified as causing human disease in Slovakia. There were 4,639 cases of enterocolitis caused by *Cl. difficile*, which is a 9% decrease compared to 2021 (when 5,100 cases were reported) but still 24% higher than the 5-year average. Cases of disease caused by A 04.7 were reported in all regions, with the highest morbidity in the Prešov Region (118.49/100,000) and the lowest morbidity in the Trnava Region.

A total of 1,647 food samples were tested for *Cl. perfringens*, returning a positivity rate of 0.2%. Out of 2,368 food samples tested for *sulphite-reducing clostridia* only two fast-food samples were positive. Of 1,726 samples from clinically ill or dead animals tested for *Clostridium* spp., 63.7% were positive. Tests for *Clostridium* spp. were also carried out on 148 samples of animal feed. The overall positivity rate was 4% and was highest in feed mixtures made from cereals. As *Cl. perfringens* is an indicator parameter for faecal water pollution, 1,506 water samples were tested for its presence. It was not detected in samples of bottled, spring, mineral and infant water but it was found in drinking water. Tests for *sulphite-reducing clostridia* were carried out on 200 water samples. The bacteria were detected in 41.5% of samples, whereas all positive findings were in surface water samples, which had a 94% positivity rate for 85 samples.

22. *Staphylococcus aureus* (coagulase positive staphylococci and their toxins)

Staphylococcus aureus is a Gram-positive coccus bacterium that is found in more than 50% of healthy people. In addition to causing infections in its own right, it also produces pathogenic toxins. The consumption of food containing staphylococcal enterotoxins is a cause of food poisoning. All kinds of contaminated food can be a source of disease but especially food for direct consumption rich in proteins. In 2020, there were 43 outbreaks in EU countries caused by toxins from *Staphylococcus aureus*.

No cases of unspecified intestinal infection caused by *S. aureus* bacteria were reported in 2022.

A total of 10,575 food samples were tested for coagulase-positive staphylococci. The set limits were exceeded in 1.73% of samples. Food types in which the limits were frequently exceeded were breast milk (7.14%), milk and dairy products (7.88%) and frozen creams and ice creams (1.80%). Staphylococcal enterotoxin was not detected in any of the samples. Enterotoxin production was demonstrated in 33.3 % of isolates from breast milk. Regarding clinically ill animals, tests on 2,388 samples for *S. aureus* returned a 17.46% positivity rate. Out of 27,349 samples of water and environmental swabs, *S. aureus* was detected in 2.38%, with the largest number of positive swabs coming from hospitals. Toxin-producing isolates were also most likely to be found on swabs from the hospital environment. Antimicrobial resistance was monitored in 1065 samples from food, animals, water and the environment. Resistance was observed in 9.39% of samples. In food, 19.48% of the positive isolates were methicillin-resistant *S. aureus*, the highest rate of resistance was found in turkey meat – 30.69%. In 445 samples from various animal species, methicillin resistance was detected in 1.57% of *S. aureus* isolates. Analysis of 389 isolates from aquatic and environmental samples found resistance to methicillin at a rate of 12.34%. No resistance was detected in isolates swabs taken in food establishments.

23. *Enterococcus* spp.

Enterococcus spp. is a genus of Gram-positive cocci made up of more than 50 species, many of which belong to the normal intestinal microbiota of humans and animals. Some species are causative agents of urogenital tract infections, bacteraemia, endocarditis, and infections of pelvic soft tissue and postoperative wounds. Because enterococci have both natural and acquired resistance against antibiotics, they represent a high risk in hospitals.

While *E. faecalis* is the more frequently detected species, *E. faecium* is more problematic because of its resistance, especially to vancomycin. In veterinary medicine, this trend is not yet as pronounced as in human medicine, but the incidence of urinary tract infections caused by enterococci is increasing. The presence of enterococci in water is one of the indicators of faecal contamination.

In 2022, there was one report of disease caused by *Enterococcus* spp.; infection took place in healthcare.

Analysis of 5 food samples had a 100% positivity rate. Of 14,510 water samples, 5.6% were above the limit or positive. Of 17,777 samples from the environment, 2% showed the presence of the genus *Enterococcus* spp.; the largest number of positive samples came from animal by-products. Antibiotic-resistant enterococci were found in a sample of wastewater. Resistance to ampicillin and vancomycin predominated.

24. Lyssavirus

Rabies is caused by RNA viruses from the genus *Lyssavirus*. This disease affects all types of warm-blooded animals and is transmissible to humans. After penetrating the body, it spreads to the central nervous system, where it multiplies and causes inflammation of the brain, from which it later continues through nerve fibres to the salivary glands and saliva. The incubation period is 1 to 3 months. Among animals, foxes are particularly susceptible to rabies. After the onset of rabies, the mortality rate is 100%. Protective vaccination is the only effective measure.

The last case of human rabies was recorded in Slovakia in 1990.

In 2022, examination of 1,029 animals for rabies returned a positive result in 3 cases. As part of the eradication programme, 735,592 vaccination doses were laid for the oral vaccination of foxes.

25. Influenza virus

Influenza is among the oldest infectious and transmissible diseases of humans and animals. It is caused by an RNA virus. The most dangerous group are the type A influenza viruses that infect humans, several species of mammals and a wide variety birds. The genus *Influenza virus* A also includes avian influenza viruses with reservoirs in waterfowl. The infection causes a wide spectrum of symptoms in birds, from a mild course to a highly contagious and rapidly fatal disease.

In 2022, there were 161,053 reports of influenza and influenza-like diseases in Slovakia with the highest incidence in the Trnava Region. Age-specific morbidity was highest in the 0 to 5-year-old age group and lowest in people over 60. Otherwise unspecified influenza A viruses were a causal factor in more cases of disease than unspecified influenza B viruses.

The VI in Zvolen tested 1992 blood samples from 129 poultry farming holdings without any positive findings. Tests for the nucleic acid of avian flu virus were carried out on 34 samples from birds living in the wild and 374 samples from domestic poultry. Positive results were recorded for 22 samples.

26. Tick-borne encephalitis virus (TBEV)

Tick-borne encephalitis (TBE) is a viral disease affecting humans and warm-blooded animals. The incubation period is 7 to 28 days. The disease usually has a two-phase clinical course. The first phase resembles flu and is followed by a symptom-free period lasting 1 – 20 days. Typical second-phase symptoms are headaches, photophobia, double vision and vomiting. The mortality rate is 0.5–2%, while almost 10% of patients subsequently suffer from various neurological problems. TBEV has its reservoirs in rodents and it is transmitted by ticks. TBEV can also be transmitted via the alimentary route, for example through milk from infected animals. The best form of protection is vaccination.

In 2022 there were 205 cases of Central European tick-borne encephalitis which is double the number in 2021 and 54% above the five-year average. The highest age-specific morbidity was in the age category 45 to 54 years. The most common cause was tick bite (139 cases). Three outbreaks were reported – one from the Prešov Region and two from the Banská Bystrica Region, with the probable factor of transmission in each case being unpasteurized sheep's milk and products made from it. In 2022, the death of a man in the 45–54 age group from the Trenčín Region was reported. Neither a tick bite nor consumption of unpasteurized products was identified as a causal factor. The patient was unvaccinated.

Fig. 5 Incidence of Tick-Borne Encephalitis in Slovakia in 2022

In 2022, analysis of 113 milk samples for TBEV returned one positive result, representing 0.88% positivity. The VI in Zvolen used the RT-PCR method to examine 7 samples of native blood from goats with a negative result. The BMC Institute of Virology at the Slovak Academy of Sciences examined 46 individual samples of human-biting ticks without a positive finding.

27. West Nile virus

WNV is the causative agent of West Nile fever. Birds are the reservoir and main host of the virus, while various types of mosquitoes that suck the infected blood of birds serve as vectors. Humans and horses can also be hosts, but the virus cannot be transmitted from them to other vectors. Infection can also develop after organ transplantation, blood transfusion, or through the placenta. The incubation period is 2 – 15 days. Most infections are asymptomatic; about 20% of patients develop flu-like symptoms. In a few cases, serious symptoms such as encephalitis, meningoencephalitis or meningitis may develop. Elderly and immunocompromised individuals are at higher risk of developing severe symptoms. In 2021, there were 139 cases of human infection in the EU/EEA, ten of which were fatal.

In 2022, there was one reported case of human West Nile fever in humans in Slovakia; this was the second documented case of the disease in humans in Slovakia.

No acute WNV infection in horses was reported in 2022.

28. Dengue virus

Dengue fever is caused by a virus whose vector is the mosquito species *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus*. Its incubation period is 3 to 14 days. The disease may have a febrile course or it may appear as a haemorrhagic fever. In 1970, Dengue fever was endemic only in nine countries outside Europe.

One case of disease was reported in 2022 (morb. 0.02/100,000) after no case was reported the year before. All cases of disease reported in the past were imported.

29. Hantaviruses

Hantaviruses cause haemorrhagic fevers in humans but are not transmissible from person to person. Their reservoir is rodents, which shed the virus through urine, faeces and saliva. Humans usually become infected by inhaling contaminated dust. In Europe, including Slovakia, there are several types of hantaviruses that cause this disease, the most common causative agent is the Puumala virus, which causes disease with a mild course. A more severe form of disease is associated with the Dobrava-Belgrade virus, which can sometimes be fatal.

A total of 84 cases were reported in 2022 (morb. 1.54/100,000), which is a decrease of 28.2% compared to the previous year. Cases occurred in all age groups except children aged 0 years. The Prešov Region had the most cases.

30. Norwalk virus

Norwalk virus (NoV) is a small, highly contagious virus whose only reservoir is humans. Transmission takes place through the faecal-oral route or contaminated food and drinks. The incubation period is from 12 to 72 hours, the disease is manifested by severe watery diarrhoea, vomiting, nausea, abdominal pain and high temperature. Symptoms last 1 to 3 days. Uncooked foods are especially risky.

There were 3,334 reported cases of disease caused by Norwalk virus in 2022, which is almost twice as many as in the previous year. The groups with the highest age-specific morbidity were children aged 0 years and 1–4 years. There were 78 outbreaks, of which 18 were of a larger size. Nosocomial infection was reported in 330 cases.

Analysis of eight food samples for the presence of the virus detected norovirus RNA – genotype GII – in one sample.

31. Rotavirus

Rotavirus is an RNA virus that mutates and recombines easily, is stable and capable of rapid multiplication. It can survive in the air and on contaminated surfaces for several days. It is transmitted through the faecal-oral route, through consumption of contaminated food, or contact with contaminated objects. Its incubation period is 1 to 3 days. Early symptoms include fever, vomiting and abdominal pain. Children under the age of five are at high risk from the disease. The best form of protection against infection is vaccination.

There were 3,660 reports of illness caused by intestinal infection with rotavirus in 2022. A total of 52 outbreaks were recorded, of which 5 were of a larger size. The highest morbidity was recorded in the Prešov Region and the highest age-specific morbidity was recorded in children aged 0 years. Nosocomial infection was reported in 228 cases. A total of 18 cases were imported.

Food and water were not tested for the presence of the virus.

Fig. 6 Incidence of Rotavirus Diarrhoea by District in Slovakia in 2022.

32. Hepatitis A virus – HAV

Hepatitis A virus (HAV) is a causative agent of acute inflammatory liver disease whose main reservoir is humans. The infection spreads through the faecal-oral route or contaminated water and food.

Since 2020, a significant decrease in morbidity has been observed, which is probably related to preventative measures, including those against COVID 19. In 2022, there were 62 cases of HAV (B15) in Slovakia, which is a 5.4-fold increase compared to 2021. In contrast to the previous year when no epidemics were recorded, an epidemic of HAV disease broke out on the Lunik housing estate in Košice in 2022 and continued into 2023. Doctors reported 16 cases starting from 9 December 2022 and in the early months of 2023 a total of 182 people fell ill. No foodstuffs were tested for the hepatitis A virus in 2022.

33. Hepatitis E virus – HEV

Hepatitis E is an infectious viral liver disease that spreads through the faecal-oral route, contaminated water, food and transfusions. Its incubation period ranges from 14 to 70 days. The most common route of HEV transmission is the consumption of raw or under-cooked pork, venison, liver and products made from them. The WHO estimates that there were 20 million new HEV infections in 2022, with over 3 million cases of acute hepatitis and more than 44,000 deaths per year.

In 2022 there were 81 cases of disease in Slovakia with the highest incidence being in the Prešov, Nitra and Košice Regions.

The University of Veterinary Medicine and Pharmacy in Košice carried out tests for HEV on a total 157 food samples, including pork meat (n=44), pork liver (n=32), beef (n=8), veal (n=2), liver pate (n=40) and sausage (n=31). The samples were collected from all retail chains

in Poprad and Košice in cooperation with RVFA Poprad and RVFA Košice-mesto. The presence of HEV RNA was not confirmed in any of the samples.

Fig. 7 Incidence of Human HEV by District in Slovakia in 2022

34. Enteroviruses

Enterovirus (EV) is a genus of RNA viruses in which several species affect animals and seven species can infect the human population. Polioviruses (PV) are the causative agents of poliomyelitis (polio), a highly contagious disease that can result in lifelong paralysis or death. Non-polio enteroviruses (NPEV) are among the most common human infectious viruses. They are mainly spread through the faecal-oral route. New-born infants, children and immunocompromised people are the most at risk. While polio viruses damage the nerve cells that control muscles and cause paralysis, Coxsackieviruses cause inflammation of the upper respiratory tract.

The NRC for IEV confirmed enterovirus infection in 3 patients. The NRC for poliomyelitis confirmed enterovirus infection in 46 samples from 39 patients. EV was isolated in 46 samples of wastewater, with PV type 3 SL being isolated in two samples from one site.

Considering global migration patterns and the fact that two cases of polio were reported in Ukraine in 2021 – a 17-month-old unvaccinated girl from Rivne Oblast in north-west Ukraine in October 2021, for whom the causal agent was a circulating, vaccine-derived poliovirus type 2, and an unvaccinated 12-year-old girl from Zakarpattia Oblast in south-west Ukraine in November 2021, for whom the causal agent was a vaccine-derived poliovirus type 1 – and a total of 19 contacts were traced for the persons infected with the virus, which did not cause paralysis, it is vital that the EV surveillance system continue to function.

35. Prions

Excessive production of prion protein and its misfolding into a pathological form is the main cause of transmissible, incurable, fatal prion diseases in humans and animals. Prions causing BSE (bovine spongiform encephalopathy) can cross the species barrier. Humans have developed a new variant of Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease (vCJD) after consuming BSE-infected beef. There has been no proven transmission to humans of the prion disease of sheep and goats – scrapie. In addition to the classic form of scrapie, there is also an atypical form of scrapie,

which has been detected in Slovakia.

In 2022, laboratories examined 356 suspected samples for CJD, which was confirmed in 22 cases, and there were a further 3 genetic cases without autopsy, which gives a morbidity rate of 0.46/100,000. The most cases were recorded in the Žilina and Banská Bystrica Regions. The highest age of the patient was 86 years.

Tests for BSE were carried out on 8,614 samples from cattle, all of which returned negative results. The last confirmed case of BSE in Slovakia was diagnosed in 2010. Tests for scrapie were carried out on 12,757 samples from sheep and goats; the positivity rate for sheep was 0.008 % (atypical form of scrapie), whereas there were no positive findings for goats, which continues the trend of previous years.

Currently, the BSE situation in Slovakia is very favourable thanks to the efforts of the veterinary services, and the situation in sheep is stable except for the single diagnosed case of atypical scrapie.

36. *Toxoplasma gondii*

Toxoplasma gondii is an intracellular parasite capable of infecting almost all species of warm-blooded animals. Toxoplasmosis has followed a decreasing trend in Slovakia since 2016. According to the latest scientific studies, about 20% of the human population is infected in Slovakia.

There were 60 reported cases of illness in 2022, which is a decrease of 23% compared to 2021 and 32% below the five-year average. Cases of illness were reported from all regions except the Bratislava Region, with the highest morbidity occurring in the Trenčín Region.

Food was not analysed for the presence of *Toxoplasma gondii*. Such analysis is not required by law despite the fact that the parasite can be contracted from certain types of meat. The State Veterinary and Food Institute and the Institute of Parasitology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences tested 1615 samples of animal blood and faeces; their positivity rate was 12.8%.

37. *Plasmodium spp.*

Parasitic protozoa of the genus *Plasmodium* are the causative agents of malaria. Their vector of transmission and definitive hosts are mosquitoes of the genus *Anopheles*, 6 species of which are also found in Slovakia. *Plasmodium falciparum* causes the most severe clinical forms of disease including liver and kidney failure, encephalopathy, cerebral oedema and coma. Malaria was endemic in the countries of the European Union until the 1970s. It was eradicated in Slovakia as early as 1963. At present, all cases of malaria in Slovakia are imported.

Two cases of disease were reported in 2022, which is three fewer than in 2021. Both cases of disease were imported from Uganda and Sudan.

38. *Babesia spp.*

Coccidia of the genus *Babesia* are obligate unicellular parasites that attack erythrocytes and cells of the reticuloendothelial system of mammals and birds. More than 100 species of *Babesia* are known, which cause babesiosis, a disease that exists in natural foci. Its main natural reservoir is in small rodents. Human infections occur after tick infestation, the incubation period of the disease is 1-6 weeks, and the symptoms of the disease are similar to those of malaria, but without the symptom of periodic fever.

As in previous years, no human babesiosis was reported in 2022.

Babesia canis was detected in two of ten *Ixodes ricinus* ticks taken from humans. Analysis of dogs' blood returned a positive result in just one of ten analysed samples. It is likely a large number of positive findings are missed when veterinary clinics do not report their diagnoses or treat dogs only for their clinical symptoms.

39. *Echinococcus* spp.

Echinococcosis is a zoonotic parasitic disease caused by tapeworms of the genus *Echinococcus*. The definitive host of *E. granulosus* is the dog, wolf, and jackal. Intermediate hosts include domestic and wild ruminants, pigs, horses, and humans. The definitive hosts of *E. multilocularis* are carnivores (mainly the red fox in Slovakia) and its intermediate hosts are small mammals. Humans become infected through contact with animals or contaminated food. Disease can take a pulmonary form characterised by coughing and weight loss or a hepatic form characterised by an enlarged abdomen and weight loss.

In 2022, there were 6 reported cases of disease, all of which had a hepatic clinical form, and the main causal agent was *E. multilocularis*. The only case of cystic echinococcosis in 2022 was an imported infection from Ukraine caused by the species *Echinococcus canadensis*, which was previously referred to as *E. granulosus*, genotype G7.

Tests for the presence of echinococci were carried out on 93 foxes in 2022. We consider the current conditions of echinococcosis monitoring, which is confined to testing foxes in specified areas of Slovakia covered by oral vaccination programmes (the Žilina and Prešov Regions), insufficient to determine the prevalence and potential further spread of *Echinococcus multilocularis*. It is highly probable that infection is much more widespread and takes place also in areas of Slovakia that are not included in monitoring and will not be covered in future. Notably, new finds of *E. multilocularis* in foxes have been recorded in south-west Slovakia in recent years.

Where animals were reported positive for *E. granulosus* in large numbers at slaughterhouses based only on visual inspection, without microscopic proof and, paradoxically, with almost no laboratory detection of this species in definitive canine hosts, it is worth considering the risk that such results are false positives. Tests on dogs in 2018 and 2019 found only eggs of *Echinococcus multilocularis*.

40. *Taenia* spp.

Taeniasis is a parasitic disease caused by this genus of tapeworms, which colonise the intestines of vertebrates, including humans. A person becomes infected by consuming contaminated food, especially by consuming raw or undercooked meat, or contaminated water. Cattle cysticercosis is caused by the larva of the tapeworm *Taenia saginata*, and cysticercosis of pigs by the larva of the tapeworm *Taenia solium*, which develop in the muscles and organs of the animals. If a person consumes such contaminated tissue, the tapeworms grow to adulthood in their intestine.

In 2022, there was one report of unspecified human taeniasis.

Findings of cysticerci in pigs and cattle at slaughterhouses are rare. Larvae were detected in only 1 pig from 617,973 examined cattle and pigs.

41. *Toxocara* spp.

Toxocariasis is one of the most widespread parasitic diseases of carnivores. It is caused by parasitic roundworms of the genus *Toxocara*. Adult roundworms live in the small intestines of carnivores. Parasite eggs excreted in faeces remain infectious for several years. When humans ingest the eggs, larvae develop in the digestive tract that can survive in tissue, but do not develop into the adult stage. Risk factors are close contact with dogs, cats or soil, eating raw meat and drinking untreated water.

The number of reports of human toxocariasis is decreasing. Whereas in 2011 there were 52 cases, the numbers fell to just 5 in 2020 and there were no reports of disease in 2021. There were three reports of human toxocariasis in 2022. In 2022, the Institute of Parasitology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences analysed samples from 216 persons suspected to have larval toxocariasis for the presence of antibodies against *Toxocara* spp. Antibodies were detected in 8 persons (3.7 %)

Tests for the genera *Toxocara* and *Toxascaris* were carried out on the faecal material and intestinal contents of their definitive hosts in 3579 samples in 2022. Roundworms or their eggs were detected in 9.72 % of samples. In the last 11 years, the prevalence of toxocariasis in examined animals in Slovakia has ranged between 8.6% and 12.6%.

42. *Trichinella* spp.

Nematodes of the genus *Trichinella* cause the serious parasitic disease trichinosis in animals and humans. If overcome, disease symptoms do not return. The main reservoir of the parasite in Slovakia is the red fox, and it is endemic in eastern and central Slovakia. In 2021, there were 77 cases of trichinosis in EU countries but no reported deaths. Bulgaria and Croatia reported the most cases.

No cases of human trichinosis were recorded in 2022. The Institute of Parasitology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences examined the blood sera of 216 patients and confirmed the presence of antibodies against *Trichinella* spp. in 1 person.

Analysis of samples from 596,127 animals for *Trichinella* spp. returned positive finds of larvae in 26 samples from foxes, martens, badgers, wolves, skunks and raccoon dogs. The prevalence of trichinosis in foxes remained below 4%, like the year before. Since 2009 farm animals have shown no positive cases, which are confined to wild animals. The dominant species in Slovakia is *Trichinella britovi*.

43. *Anisakis* spp.

Anisakis nematodes are parasites of saltwater fish that pass through up to three intermediate hosts. Although they rarely reach adulthood in humans and are usually spontaneously eliminated from the digestive tract within three weeks of infection, *Anisakis simplex* causes severe allergic reactions in humans. The disease is transmitted by raw, undercooked or incorrectly frozen fish meat or shellfish.

In 2022, just as in previous years, there were no reports of human disease caused by *Anisakis simplex*.

Only one sample was tested for the presence of larvae of the *Anisakidae* family and it did not return a positive find.

44. *Dirofilaria* spp.

Dirofilariasis is a disease caused by the species *D. immitis* and *D. repens*. Hosts include dogs, cats, and wild carnivores, while various mosquito species serve as intermediate hosts and vectors. Humans are a non-specific host. In the subacute form of disease, subcutaneous nodules form on the head, eyelids, face, neck and chest. In the pulmonary form of infection, 1 to 3 cm lesions are formed on the lungs.

In 2022, there were five confirmed cases of human heartworm disease caused by *Dirofilaria repens*.

Dog blood samples have been tested for the presence of dirofilariasis since 2005. Tests were carried out on 266 dogs in 2022, with a positivity rate of 22.18%. Whereas infections with *Dirofilaria repens* predominated in previous years, 2022 saw an alarming increase in the proportion of mono-infections with *Dirofilaria immitis*, which can cause heart failure in dogs with fatal consequences. The growing proportion of *D. immitis* is demonstrated not only by the increased number of findings of this species in dogs, but also by the first human *D. immitis* infection, which was recorded in 2021.

Annex 1 – List of Cooperating Organisations

Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Slovak Republic – National Contact Point for Scientific and Technical Cooperation with the EFSA
National Agricultural and Food Centre – Food Research Institute
National Institute of Tuberculosis, Pulmonary Diseases and Thoracic Surgery, Vyšné Hágy
Regional Public Health Authority, Banská Bystrica
Regional Public Health Authority, Komárno
Regional Public Health Authority, Košice
Regional Public Health Authority, Trenčín
Slovak Academy of Sciences – Institute of Parasitology, Košice
Slovak Academy of Sciences – BMC Institute of Virology, Bratislava
Slovak University of Technology, Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology
Slovak Medical University
State Veterinary and Food Administration of the Slovak Republic
State Veterinary and Food Institute – Veterinary and Food Institute, Bratislava
State Veterinary and Food Institute – Veterinary and Food Institute, Dolný Kubín
State Veterinary and Food Institute – Veterinary and Food Institute, Dolný Kubín, TL Prešov
State Veterinary and Food Institute – Veterinary and Food Institute, Košice
State Veterinary and Food Institute – Veterinary Institute, Zvolen
Trnava University, Faculty of Health Sciences and Social Work, Trnava
Comenius University, Faculty of Medicine, Institute of Epidemiology, Bratislava
University of Matej Bel, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Banská Bystrica
University of Pavol Jozef Šafárik, Faculty of Medicine, Košice
University of Veterinary Medicine and Pharmacy in Košice
Public Health Authority of the Slovak Republic
Water Management Research Institute, Bratislava

Annex 2 – Team of Authors

MVDr. Daniela Antolová, PhD. (Institute of Parasitology SAS)
doc. MUDr. Mária Avdičová, PhD. (RPHA BB)
MVDr. Marianna Babinčáková (SVFI DK)
Mgr. Jana Bako (NRC for viral hepatitis SMU)
MVDr. Marta Bedriová (SVFA SR)
MVDr. Girma Belay, CSc. (SMU)
doc. Ing. Lucia Bírošová, PhD. (FChFT SUT)
MVDr. Viliam Bizub (RPHA KE)
RNDr. Lucia Blaňarová, PhD. (Institute of Parasitology SAS)
prof. RNDr. Shubhada Bopegamage, CSc. - NRC for the identification of enteral viruses, SMU
Mária Borsányiová, PhD. (NRC for the identification of enteral viruses, LF SMU)
MVDr. Lenka Cabanová, PhD. (VFI DK)
MVDr. Ivana Cingel'ová Maruščáková, PhD. (UVMPH KE)
RNDr. Marianna Cichová, PhD. (WMRI)
MVDr. Tomáš Csank, PhD. (UVMPH KE)
Mgr. Eva Čechová, PhD. (VI ZV)
MVDr. Zuzana Čuvalová, PhD. (VFI DK)
Ing. Monika Dräxlerová (PHA SR)
Mgr. Gabriela Dringušová (MARD SR)
RNDr. Miriam Filipová, PhD. (VFI DK)
MUDr. Mgr. Miriam Fulová (Institute of Epidemiology FoM CU)
MVDr. Gabriela Gadusová (VFI KE)
MUDr. Dagmar Gavačová (PHA SR)
Mgr. Andrea Gažiová (PHA SR)
Prof. MVDr. Monika Halánová, PhD. (Institute of Epidemiology, FoM LF KE)
MVDr. Anna Hanzelyová (VFI DK – TL Prešov)
MVDr. Zuzana Hurníková, PhD. (Institute of Parasitology SAS)
doc. MVDr. Anna Jacková, PhD. (UVMPH KE)
MUDr. Alžbeta Janáková (SMU)
Mgr. Daniela Jankovichová (VFI DK – TL Prešov)
MVDr. Slavomír Jerg (VI ZV)
RNDr. Anna Jacková, PhD. (PHA SR)
MVDr. Martin Kasenčák (VFI DK –SL Prešov)
MVDr. Ľudmila Kazarková (VFI BA)
MUDr. Jana Kerlik, PhD. (RPHA BB)
RNDr. Renáta Kissová, PhD. (RPHA BB)
MVDr. Henrieta Kocianová (RPHA TN)
Ing. Janka Koreňová, PhD. (NAFC - ARI)
Mgr. Barbora Kotvasová (PHA SR)
Team of the Ministry of Environment laboratories at regional public health authorities
Team of staff of the veterinary and food institutes of the Slovak Republic
Team of laboratories at regional public health authorities
Ing. Janka Koreňová, PhD. (NAFC - ARI)
Ing. Daniela Korytárová (VI ZV)
Doc. MVDr. Jana Koščová, PhD. (UVMPH KE)
Mgr. Martina Kotrbancová, PhD. (Institute of Epidemiology FoM CU)
Mgr. Barbora Kotvasová (PHA SR)
MVDr. Danka Kováčová (VFI DK – TL Prešov)

Ing. Monika Krahulcová, PhD. (FChFT SUT)
RNDr. Zuzana Kubicová (VFI DK)
Mgr. Lukáš Kunštek (PHA SR)
MVDr. Daniela Kvietková (VFI BA)
MUDr. Viera Lengyelová (RPHA KE)
RNDr. Martina Ličková, PhD. (BMC Institute of Virology SAS)
MVDr. Miriam Maceková (VFI DK)
Mgr. Denisa Masárová (RPHA KN)
Mgr. Jakub O. Mihale (NRC for viral hepatitis SMU)
Mgr. Lenka Michalíková, PhD. (Trnava University)
Ing. Jana Minarovičová, PhD. (NAFC - ARI)
MVDr. Martina Miterpáková, PhD. (Institute of Parasitology SAS)
MVDr. Martin Mojžiš (SVFI DK)
Ing. Andrea Mojžišová, PhD. (VFI DK)
RNDr. Monika Musilová, RPHA BB
RNDr. Ingrid Papajová, PhD. (Institute of Parasitology SAS)
Mgr. Katarína Pastuchová (PHA SR)
Mgr. Katarína Peňazziová, PhD. (UVMPH KE)
RNDr. Jana Perželová, PhD. (Institute of Epidemiology FoM CU)
Ing. Marek Pondelík (CCTIA BA)
Mgr. Matúš Prívvara (PHA SR)
RNDr. Miloslava Prokšová, CSc. (WMRI Bratislava)
RNDr. Petra Schusterová, PhD. (UVMPH KE)
RNDr. Katarína Schwarzová, PhD. (FoM SMU BA)
Mgr. Ing. Zuzana Sirotná, MPH, MHA (PHA SR)
RNDr. Martin Sojka, PhD. (PHA SR)
doc. MUDr. Ivan Solovič, CSc. (NRT Vyšné Hágy)
Mgr. RNDr. Jozef Strhársky, PhD., MPH (NRC for toxoplasmosis)
MVDr. Katarína Strišková, PhD. (VFI BA)
doc. MUDr. Margita Špaleková, PhD. (Institute of Epidemiology FoM CU)
Mgr. Eva Špitalská, PhD. (BMC Institute of Virology SAS BA)
MVDr. Lucia Šulejová (VFI DK)
PhDr. Jana Švecová, MBA (NRT Vyšné Hágy)
MVDr. Martin Tinák (VI ZV)
Prof. MVDr. Alexandra Trbolová, PhD. (UVMPH KE)
Mgr. Daniela Valentová (VFI BA)
RNDr. Bronislava Vichová, PhD. (Institute of Parasitology SAS)
MUDr. Vanda Výrosteková, PhD. (Institute of Epidemiology FoM CU)
MVDr. Dana Zubriková, PhD. (Institute of Parasitology SAS)

Annex 3 – List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

ARD	acute respiratory disease
BMC	Biomedical Research Centre
BSE	bovine spongiform encephalopathy
CJD	Creutzfeldt-Jacob Disease
WTP	wastewater treatment plant
DSS	social care home (<i>domov sociálnych služieb</i>)
EEA	European Economic Area
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
EREN	EFSA Emerging Risks Exchange Network
EU	European Union
FChFT	Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology
HAV	Hepatitis A virus
HEV	Hepatitis E virus
HFRS	Haemorrhagic fever with renal syndrome
HUS	haemolytic uremic syndrome
morb.	morbidity
ILD	influenza-like disease
ISBN	International Standard Book Number
FoM CU	Faculty of Medicine of Comenius University in Bratislava
CNS	coagulase negative staphylococci
CPS	coagulase positive staphylococci
LB	Lyme borreliosis
LD	Legionnaire's disease
MI	Microbiology Institute
MRSA	Methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
unsp.	unspecified
NCP EFSA	National Contact Point for Scientific and Technical Cooperation with EFSA
NoV	Norwalk virus
NAFC – FRI	National Agricultural and Food Centre – Food Research Institute
	new variant of Creutzfeldt-Jacob disease
nvCJD	National Reference Centre
NRC	National Institute of Children's Diseases Bratislava
NICD	
IoPa SAS	Institute of Parasitology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences
PD	Prion disease
ca.	case
RL	reference laboratory
RNA	ribonucleic acid
RT PCR	Real time PCR - polymerase chain reaction with reverse transcription
RPHA	Regional Public Health Authority
SARI	Severe Acute Respiratory Infection
SAS	Slovak Academy of Sciences
TL	test laboratory
s.l.	<i>Borrelia burgdorferi sensu lato</i> complex
SR	Slovak Republic
SUT	Slovak University of Technology

SVFI	State Veterinary and Food Institute
TBC	tuberculosis
TBEV	Tick-borne encephalitis virus
IoE	Institute of epidemiology
TSE	transmissible spongiform encephalopathy
DHW	domestic hot water
UHB	University Hospital Bratislava
LPUH	Louis Pasteur University Hospital in Kosice
CCTIA	Central Control and Testing Institute in Agriculture Bratislava
UVMPH KE	University of Veterinary Medicine and Pharmacy in Košice
PHA SR	Public Health Authority of the Slovak Republic
IoVi SAS	Institute of Virology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences
VFI	Veterinary and Food Institute
VI	Veterinary Institute
VTEC/STEC	<i>E.coli</i> producing verotoxin/Shiga toxin
FRI	Food research institute (in Slovak: <i>Výskumný ústav potravinársky</i>)
WMRI	Water Management Research Institute
WB	Western Blot
WHO	World Health Organisation
WNV	West Nile virus

SUMMARY REPORT OF ZOOSES, ALIMENTARY AND WATER-BORNE
INFECTIONS IN THE SLOVAK REPUBLIC IN 2022

© MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURE AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT
OF THE SLOVAK REPUBLIC

FIRST EDITION

ISBN 978-80-89738-39-7